

mix, the germination percentage ranged from 0 to 2%. Growth of those seeds that did germinate was extremely poor.

This unexpected result could be explained by *T. viride* being toxic to rice but not to the other plants tested. The mechanisms for this toxicity could be either exosomatic, through the rice being especially sensitive to *T. viride* toxins released in the rhizosphere, or endosomatic, through the habit of rice of phagocytizing soil organic materials in heterophagous nutrition—toxins of *T. viride* origin might be brought into the rice root to make intimate connection with the rice cytoplasm. Thus, *T. viride* would especially affect rice but not other plants that lack the phagocytic habit.

An alternative hypothesis is that rice might have a specific requirement for a mycorrhizal symbiont that is killed by the *T. viride*, hence the poor or zero germination.

In an attempt to test these hypotheses, trials were conducted in which 100 seed lots of rice were germinated on damp filter paper after being treated with dilute solutions of antifungicides. Copper oxychloride, benlate, and hydrogen peroxide were used in weak

Germination and growth of lots of 100 seeds of rice variety PSBRc4 HD 437 on filter paper subjected to antifungal treatments.

Factor	Treatment				
	None	1% hydrogen peroxide	1% copper oxychloride	1% benomyl benlate	0.01% <i>Spirulina platensis</i>
Germination (%)	98	98	98	100	100
Total wet weight (g) at 20 d postplanting	5.627	6.305	6.496	5.652	7.730
Maximum stem height (mm) at 19 d postplanting	50	60	57	53	59
Max. root length (mm) at 6 d	20	25	35	22	30

concentrations that did not affect the germination of other plant species (barley, oat, and wheat). One hundred seed lots were also germinated in the presence of a small amount of *Spirulina platensis*, a commonly available cyanobacterium. The experiments were repeated with dehulled rice seeds. Three replicates of all trials were conducted.

Compared with the controls, all the antifungicides stimulated growth. Germination and growth were enhanced over the controls when rice was germinated in the presence of *S. platensis* (see table).

These results suggest that microorganisms can affect the early growth of rice. In practical management, fungi-

cides can improve germination. Seed-raising mixes contaminated with *Trichoderma* spp. or other fungi that are inhibitors to growth should be avoided.

Another interesting result from this work is that germination and growth might be enhanced if a small quantity of *S. platensis* is added to the seeds at planting time. *S. platensis* is a N₂-fixing photoautotroph that grows actively in damp conditions, thus possibly increasing the N available to the seedlings as well as providing an additional carbon source. It also contains powerful antifungal and antiviral compounds that could protect the seed and emerging seedling from attack by microorganisms. ■

Integrated pest management — insects

Evolving insecticide use and practices at IIRI

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With growing awareness of the concerns associated with pesticide (especially insecticide) use, IIRI has acted over the past decade to play a lead role in both reducing insecticide use and promoting safe pesticide use for people and the environment. In addition to the direct steps taken at the IIRI experiment station, a book has also been produced by IIRI (in 1995) addressing areas of concern related to pesticides, farmer health, and the rice environment. The improvements made at the IIRI experiment station include

1. Implementation of a trained pesticide applicators (TPA) program (1987).
2. A ban on World Health Organization (WHO) Category One pesticides (1989).
3. Implementation of a regular scheme to monitor insect, disease, and weed populations in fields (1991).
4. Endorsement of integrated pest management (IPM) as the standard for pest management at the IIRI station (1995).
5. Further changes in application methods and monitoring of fields (1997).

We detail each of these steps below.

1. Trained Pesticide Applicators program (1987)

To improve the safe use of pesticides, IIRI introduced a system of "authorized pesticide applications" in 1987. (The name was subsequently changed to trained pesticide applicators, TPA.) The system includes guidelines for (1) certification process (training), (2) routine medical examinations and health reporting, (3) use of personal protective equipment, (4) job rotation, (5) decontamination facilities, and (6) safe product disposal.

This system ensures that pesticide applications are made by trained staff, resulting in improved application with benefits to both users and the environment.

2. Ban on the use of Category One pesticides (1989)

In 1989, IRRI management banned the use at the IRRI experiment station of products defined by WHO as Category One such as parathion, that is, products that are extremely and highly hazardous to human health). Coming after the implementation of the TPA system, this move had further benefits for both users and the environment.

3. Implementation of regular pest monitoring (1991)

To improve the basis for deciding whether a pesticide application was necessary, IRRI introduced a regular monitoring system in 1991. With this system, all fields and glasshouses were monitored weekly by trained staff to determine insect, disease, rat, and weed pressures; the golden apple snail (*Pomacea* sp.) was monitored at planting. Critical pest levels for recommended control were established. If a doubt arose about the need for an application, the monitoring team would revisit a field and, where necessary, call upon expertise from IRRI's Entomology and Plant Pathology Division.

4. Integrated pest management as a standard (1995)

The IRRI Experiment Station Committee (chaired by the deputy director general for research and with division heads as members) made IPM the standard for pest control on the IRRI experiment station in 1995. The growing knowledge base for IPM of insects indicates that insecticide applications during the initial stages (e.g., first 30-40 d) of the rice crop are generally unnecessary. It is worth mentioning that although IPM is the standard, more intensive insect control is permitted depending on the experimental objectives and/or susceptibility of the materials in the trial.

5. Further changes in application and researcher monitoring (1997)

With individual researchers becoming increasingly aware of the benefits of IPM, the responsibility for field monitoring was given to the individual scientists in 1997. The experiment station retains expertise for validating monitoring results as required. In 1997, experiment station staff members introduced boom spraying where possible and the use of a controlled pressure valve (for backpack sprayers). Both practices improve the uniformity of spray applications and improve safety for users. Recent improvements in land leveling will also help improve pest control (especially for weeds and the golden apple snail).

In the IRRI glasshouses, pesticide use has been reduced by implementing an annual month-long greenhouse shutdown (thus breaking insect life cycles) and using colored sticky traps and milder hand-spray insecticidal soaps. Biological control agents represent a further option to be pursued.

Changes in pesticide use

Insecticide use (active ingredients ha^{-1} season $^{-1}$) has dropped dramatically at IRRI in recent years, especially when IPM was introduced in 1995 (see figure). Both fungicide and molluscicide use have also fallen slightly.

Based on informal observations, reduced insecticide use at IRRI has

resulted in increases in the number of birds and beneficial insects seen in fields. In addition, field observations have shown that control of the rice whorl maggot (*Hydrellia philippina*) and defoliators such as leaffolders (e.g., *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*) is rarely required. Planthoppers (e.g., *Nilaparvata lugens*) have only been a problem in fields that were sprayed early, and green leafhoppers (GLH-*Nephotettix virescens*) have occasionally been a problem, but primarily only when rice tungro virus disease has been present (GLH being the primary vector of tungro). Rice bug (*Leptocorisa oratorius*) is occasionally a problem on crops planted out of synchrony with other crops.

Challenges

The practices introduced at IRRI have led to a reduced and safer use of pesticides (especially insecticides), with benefits to the environment and IRRI staff. But several challenges remain, including better systems for stem borer monitoring and control, better understanding of the effects of stem borer damage at high yield potential levels, improved control of the golden apple snail with reduced use of molluscicide, and mechanization of pesticide application (boom spraying and the use of tractor-mounted sprayers with special narrow-design wheels), and thus further reductions in pesticide use.

Stem borers also merit attention. They are more problematic to control

Use of pesticides (kg ai ha⁻¹) at IRRI experiment station (DS = dry season, WS = wet season).

than other pests because once the damage is apparent, it is essentially too late to effectively control the pest; thus, farmers and researchers may be tempted to use prophylactic applications for "safety." Infestations of stem borer during the 1996 dry season were

the highest seen for many years (infestation varied from a 0 to 8% proportion of total panicles infested). Although the damage looked spectacular, it has been repeatedly shown that damage at low to moderate

yield levels has little to no effect on crop yield. Data presently being collected also suggest that plants retain sufficient yield component plasticity even at higher yield levels (>8 t ha⁻¹) to compensate for damaged panicles. ■

Integrated pest management — weeds

Butachlor safener combinations for weed control in direct-seeded puddled rice

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Weed competition is a major constraint to the productivity of broadcast-seeded rice. Although manual weeding controls weeds effectively, because of the absence of rows, it is difficult, time-consuming, and costly. In addition, labor is scarce. Butachlor, the recommended herbicide, controls weeds effectively, but is toxic to germinating rice seedlings. The use of a safener, an antidote, protects rice seedlings from butachlor injury effectively without any adverse effect on weed control.

A field experiment was conducted during the 1994 and 1995 wet seasons at HPKV, Palampur (32° 6' N, 76° 3' E,

1,290 m altitude). The soil of the test site was silty clay loam, with pH 6.9, 1.2% organic C, 364 kg available N ha⁻¹, 21 kg available P ha⁻¹, and 326 kg available K ha⁻¹. Sprouted seeds of variety HPU2216 were sown at 100 kg ha⁻¹ by the broadcast method onto puddled soil on 19 Jun 1994 and 26 Jun 1995. The treatments (see table) were evaluated in a randomized block design with three replications. The data analyzed by standard analysis of variance and treatment means were compared with the LSD test at the 5% level.

Weed samples were taken from a 25 cm × 25 cm area and oven-dried at 70 °C, and dry weight was recorded. Grain yield was recorded from a 7.5-m² net plot area. Plant samples from a 0.5-m² area were taken at harvest to record yield components. The emergence count was recorded from a 0.5-m² area at 18 d after sowing (DAS). The dominant weeds were *Echinochloa crus-galli*,

E. colona, *Ammania baccifera*, *Scirpus* sp., *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *C. esculentus*, *Aeschynomene indica*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Commelina forskalli*.

Butachlor without safener applied at 2 or 7 DAS caused toxicity to rice seedlings, but this was significantly less when applied at 7 DAS than at 2 DAS. Other butachlor safener combinations also caused acute toxicity symptoms, but rice plants were able to recover. Butachlor at 2 kg ha⁻¹ + safener at 0.188 kg ha⁻¹ (7 DAS) was the most effective combination for yield and weed control. Rice yield of the butachlor at 1.5 kg ha⁻¹ + safener at 0.188 kg ha⁻¹ (2 and 7 DAS) treatments was equal to that of the crop that received two hand weeding. At each time of application (i.e., 2 or 7 DAS), butachlor with safener at 0.094 or 0.188 kg ha⁻¹ controlled weeds effectively and increased rice grain yield significantly over its application without safener (see table). ■

Effect of butachlor safener combinations on emergence count, panicles m², panicle weight, grain yield, and weed dry weight in direct-seeded puddled rice.

Treatment	Time of application (DAS) ^a	(kg ai ha ⁻¹)	Emergence count (g m ⁻²)		Panicles (no. m ⁻²)		Panicle weight (g)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)	
			1994	1995	1994	1995	1994	1995	1994	1995	1994 ^b	1995
			Butachlor ^c	2	1.5	199	148	324	168	1.53	1.58	3.4
Butachlor + safener ^d	2	1.5 + 0.094	292	239	420	234	1.68	1.75	4.5	2.7	3.24 (10.1)	77
Butachlor + safener	2	1.5 + 0.188	316	265	467	248	1.75	1.81	5.0	3.0	2.41 (6.8)	43
Butachlor	7	1.5	257	195	373	195	1.55	1.61	4.0	2.0	4.76 (25.5)	81
Butachlor + safener	7	1.5 + 0.094	323	261	427	242	1.71	1.77	4.5	3.0	3.93 (15.1)	47
Butachlor + safener	7	1.5 + 0.188	342	281	463	261	1.77	1.88	4.9	3.2	3.37 (11.0)	31
Safener	2	0.188	368	324	327	188	1.35	1.40	3.4	1.2	8.97 (80.2)	399
Butachlor + safener	7	2.0 + 0.188	338	272	492	295	1.79	1.92	5.2	3.7	1.10 (0.8)	12
Hand weeding twice	25 & 45	–	365	324	472	264	1.83	1.95	5.0	3.3	3.63 (12.7)	27
Unweeded check	–	–	361	329	296	184	1.32	1.39	3.0	1.2	9.58 (91.7)	406
LSD (0.05)			25	40	59	40	0.17	0.20	0.6	0.6	1.15	21

^aDays after sowing. ^bData transformed to $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$ transformation. Values in parentheses are the means of original values. ^cFormulation: Trapp 50 EC. ^dTrade name S901A, chemical name 4,6 dichloro-2-phenyl pyrimidine.